

Positionality statements: A tool to open YOUR research

Amsterdam, 26 September 2025
Tamarinde Haven, Bogdana Huma

Introductions

What drew you to your current research or professional role?

Neutrality

Who decides what is neutral?

Neutraliteit bestaat niet

NOS-hoofdredacteur Van Cann zegt dat de NOS-journalisten uitzoeken hoe het zit en de kijkers en luisteraars vertellen wat ze hebben aangetroffen ([Verdieping, 22 september](#)). Feiten achterhalen dus. Ik deel graag mee welke feiten ik vanmorgen heb aangetroffen: havermout is op, slecht geparkeerde fiets viel en rugpijn, we moeten een nieuwe matras kopen. Feiten die niet op nos.nl stonden, omdat ze niet belangrijk zijn. Dat betekent dat iemand toch, op z'n minst, zal moeten selecteren wat wel en niet belangrijk is. Oftewel: neutraliteit bestaat niet, ook niet bij de NOS. Het is niet wenselijk of onwenselijk, het is onmogelijk. Als de journalisten bij NOS neutraal proberen te zijn, wie of wat bepaalt dan wat we in het nieuws zien? Een zorgelijke gedachte.

Lieke Asma Amsterdam

Background: Standpoint theory

Donna Haraway

Dorothy Smith

Patricia Hill Collins

Standpoint theory

Knowledge production is always situated within a particular context; therefore, it is never purely objective or neutral.

- An individual's race, class, gender, sexuality, culture, and life experience fundamentally shape their understanding of the world, including the assumptions they bring to their research

Source: Jacky Fleming - The Trouble with Women

Standpoint theory

Acknowledging one's standpoint requires reflection

- Positionality statements are a tool for identifying how a researcher's multiple identities may influence various aspects of the research process (e.g., topic selection, formulation of hypothesis/research question, data collection, data analysis, write-up etc.)

Positionality statements

You as a researcher

Relationship with participants

Paradigm in which you do research

It takes two flints to start a fire: A focus group study into PhD supervision for responsible research

Tamarinde Haven

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I (PhD, female, extensive experience with focus groups and interviews) conducted the focus groups employed as a postdoc and later as an assistant professor. I co-lead a European special interest group on training for supervisors and leadership. Besides my academic career, I train supervisors to mentor their PhD candidates toward research integrity. Except for two social scientists who I met at a conference before, no previous relationships existed between me and the participants.

Can—and should—automaticity be self-reported using a single item? A secondary analysis of 16 datasets

Benjamin Gardner Phillippa Lally, Amanda L. Rebar

Researchers are increasingly encouraged to document and reflect upon their assumptions, beliefs and motivations and how these may have informed the research process, that is, their *positionality* (Jamieson et al., [2023](#)). [.....]

[...] We differed in our prioritisation of conceptual versus practical concerns. Author BG, prioritising conceptual integrity, was sceptical about the possibility of capturing the complexity of automaticity via a single item, regardless of its psychometric properties (see too, e.g. Orbell & Verplanken, [2015](#)). PL and ALR prioritised practicality and ethicality. [...]

Porridge and misogyny: Rationalising inconspicuous misogyny in morning television shows

Feminism & Psychology

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Before moving forward, we also need to clarify our standpoint and how it informed our analysis. The intersection of our identities as feminist, White, European, middle-class, heterosexual ciswomen with higher education informed our interest in undertaking a study on contemporary manifestations of misogyny, and provided the cultural background against which we analysed the interactions. We believe that, together with the reviewed literature, these category memberships enabled us to make sense of participants' conduct (Kitzinger, 2000). It is likely that our selection of extracts and, to some extent, the presentation of the findings, has been guided by our sociocultural background as well as by our support of feminist ideas (Wilkinson, 1988). Still, in line with the discursive psychological approach, in the analysis below, we support all observations with evidence from the data, which ensures the transparency and integrity of our analytic endeavour.

Time for practice!

Photo by [Jordan Sanchez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Warm - up

Write down everything that comes to mind when you think about coffee?

Exercise 1

What does openness in research mean to you?
Why is it important?

Exercise 2A

What are your **assumptions** about[fill in with your research topic]?

How did they evolve over the time you spent researching this topic?

Alternative Prompt:

What would make for good qualitative open science?

Exercise 2B

What are your values, beliefs, and backgrounds?

How might or could these values, beliefs, and backgrounds affect or shape your research into
[fill in with your research topic]?

Alternative:

How might or could these values, beliefs, and backgrounds affect or shape your work as a research supporter or administrator?

Exercise 2C:

What are the different perspectives of your research team members on[fill in with your research topic]?

To what extent did they appear as similar, or different, and how would you deal with that?

Draft your own Positionality Statement

Please draft your own positionality statement here, reflecting on your **role** and **identity** in relation to the **context and setting of the research** (e.g., were you an insider or outsider, etc.), what was the relation with the **research subjects**, and what **specific assumptions** do you bring based on your **research paradigm**?

The Iterative Inquiry Spiral (from Markham, 2017)

The process of uncovering one's assumptions about a topic resembles travelling down a spiral in order to repeatedly examine ideas, beliefs and thoughts to identify where they come from and what lies behind them.

Open Discussion

- How does this relate to Open Science and reproducibility?
- How much detail should be included in a positionality statement?
- What else can you do to enhance the transparency of your research processes?

“I’m not just made for men”: Managing misogyny in online sex work

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Reflexivity

This study was influenced by the positionality of the research team, comprised of eight individuals (five undergraduate psychology students; all White; three cisgender women, one trans woman, and one nonbinary person; and three mentors, all White women), none of whom have previous experience with online sex work. The project was developed out of the group's interest in the burgeoning area of online sex work, aiming to investigate the motivations, benefits, and tolls of engaging in online sex work. This paper was born from the first author's particular interest in the juxtaposition between empowerment and misogyny. The positionality of the researchers may have influenced the questions asked and/or the interpretation of the data. A separate manuscript analyzing the same dataset focuses on experiences of stigma (see [Stutz et al., 2022](#)).

Research Article

Perspectives on the Strong Black Woman Schema Based on SES Among Black Women: A Qualitative Study Using the Agentic-Communal Model

My positionality as a Black woman inevitably informed both the interview process and the interpretation of the data in this study. I, the first author, am a Black American, cisgender woman and 5th year graduate student at a Hispanic-serving institution. I was raised in an upper-middle class home with two parents who have each obtained a master's degree. My research is interdisciplinary and examines the racialized gender stereotypes impacting Black women and the contexts in which stereotypes (i.e., the SBW) impact Black women's health outcomes. I have spent the entirety of my scholarship exploring this particular phenomenon that is exclusive to Black women and have a personal connection with the SBW schema. These experiences likely influenced how I interpreted the data collected; thus, myself and the second author used qualitative checks to minimize potential bias. I attempted to intentionally engage with the research via memoing to (a) keep track of how my personal thoughts and experiences may impact my interpretations of the data; and (b) strengthen my ability to connect with and bring an in-depth understanding of the participants' experiences to coding. The second author is a white American, cisgender woman, and professor at a Hispanic-serving institution. She has an M.A. and Ph.D. in Social Psychology and an M.S. in Clinical Mental Health Counseling. Her program of research investigates how the intersection of identities such as gender, race, sexual orientation, and social class impact relationships with power. She has extensive experience with qualitative, mixed methods, and quantitative research designs.

Picture by Claitia Moy on Unsplash

CONTEXT:
-NETWORK

WEBINAR: QUALITATIVE OPEN RESEARCH: MEANINGFUL EXCHANGE AND MUTUAL LEARNING

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Nicki Lisa Cole
Know Center

Michelle Jamieson
Edinburgh Napier
University

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Organised by:
Bogdana Huma & Elliott Hoey

Upcoming Events

16 October 25, 10 - 12 hrs, Webinar: Qualitative Open Research

24 October 25, Open Science Festival

12 December 25, VU/hybrid, Symposium: Qualitative Innovation in Action

19 January 26, Leiden: NLRN Symposium Culture Shift: Embedding
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